

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of ZrO(II) and Th(IV) with Phloroacetophenone

R. C. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Bipin Bihari College, Jhansi-284001

Manuscript received 18 September 1973; revised 16 March 1974; accepted 17 April 1974

Proton-ligand stability constants of Phloroacetophenone (2,4,6 trihydroxy acetophenone) have been calculated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% Dioxane—H₂O system by Irving & Rossotti technique and found to be 8.608. Stoichiometry (1:2) of ZrO(II) and Th(IV)-Phloroacetophenone have been studied by pH ratio titration method. Stability constants of complexes have been evaluated by Calvia and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method in 50% Dioxane—H₂O system at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ in an ionic strength of 0.1M in 1.0M NaClO₄—stability constants for ZrO(II) at pH 2.0 to 7.0 and for Th(IV) at pH 2.0 to 3.20 found to be 10.403 and 10.401 respectively.

O-HYDROXYACETOPHENONES behave as strong complexing agent owing to the presence of -OH groups on 'ortho' position for coordination with metal ions. Hence complexes of metal ions with *o*-hydroxyacetophenones have been investigated by different group of workers. But interreaction of phloroacetophenone (2,4,6-trihydroxy acetophenone) referred to herein as PAP) with metal ions have been not reported so far, therefore in this paper study of the proton-ligand stability of PAP and its complexes with ZrO(II) and Th(IV) have been made.

Experimental

PAP¹ was prepared by mixing dry phloroglucinol, anhydrous acetonitril, sodium dried ether and fused anhydrous ZnCl₂ in a vessel kept in ice—salt mixture. The HCl gas was passed for 2 hrs. The substance was kept overnight in ice-chest and HCl gas was again passed. After leaving for 72 hrs. in ice-chest the yellowish solid obtained was dissolved in hot water and refluxed for 2 hrs. The PAP was purified by decolorising charcoal and recrystallised with hot water.

Dioxane was dried with Na and distilled twice² Th(NO₃)₄ and ZrOCl₂ solutions were prepared in airfree-conductivity water and metal content were estimated gravimetrically by converting into oxalates and then ignited as oxides. All the chemicals used were Anal-R (B.D.H. or equivalent).

pH-measurements were carried out on radiometer pH-meter (PHM-4) and the temperature was kept constant to $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. All the pH-titrations were carried out in an ionic-strength of 0.1M NaClO₄ and 50% dioxane—H₂O system by standard carbonate free NaOH. Correction for pH-measurements in dioxane-H₂O system were made as described by Van Uitert and Haas³. The proton-ligand stability constant of PAP was determined by Irving and Rossotti⁴ techniques by using the following equa-

tions. In calculation concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations.

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \left\{ \frac{(V'' - V')}{(V^0 + V')} \cdot \frac{(N + E^0)}{T_L^0} \right\}$$

and

$$\log pK_H = \beta + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$$

The following sets were prepared for pH-titrations keeping 50% dioxane—H₂O system.

- (i) 5 ml. of 0.05M HClO₄ + 4.75 ml. of 1 M NaClO₄ + 15.25 ml. of H₂O.
- (ii) 5 ml. of 0.05M HClO₄ + 10 ml. of 0.05M PAP + 4.25 ml. of 1M NaClO₄ + 5.75 ml. of H₂O.
- (iii) 5 ml. of 0.05M HClO₄ + 10 ml. of 0.05M PAP + 3.75 ml. of 1M NaClO₄ + 5 ml. of 0.01M Th(NO₃)₄ + 1.25 ml. of H₂O.
- (iv) 5 ml. of 0.05M HClO₄ + 10 ml. of 0.05M PAP + 4.1 ml. of 1M NaClO₄ + 5 ml. of 0.01M ZrOCl₂ + 0.9 ml. of H₂O.

Results and Discussion

pH readings for all sets were plotted against the moles of NaOH. The curve for set II show only one point of inflection, hence there is only one dissociable hydrogen ion in PAP. Therefore the value of Y was kept equal to one in calculating the proton-ligand stability constant of PAP. The table 1 is obtained from calculations for proton-ligand stability constant of PAP.

\bar{n}_A and log pK_H were plotted which gives the proton-ligand stability constant of PAP equal to 8.608 at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The dissociation constant of the PAP thus is 2.455×10^{-9} .

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT.

pH	V'	V''	\bar{n}_A	log <i>pkH</i>
7.5	1.42 ml	1.50 ml	0.9644	8.9333
7.6	1.42 "	1.55 "	0.9422	8.8125
7.7	1.42 "	1.60 "	0.9199	8.7605
7.8	1.42 "	1.67 "	0.8889	8.7030
7.9	1.43 "	1.74 "	0.8622	8.6964
8.0	1.43 "	1.80 "	0.8356	8.7060
8.1	1.43 "	1.88 "	0.8000	8.7021
8.2	1.44 "	2.00 "	0.7512	8.6799
8.3	1.44 "	2.10 "	0.8068	8.6822
8.4	1.45 "	2.20 "	0.6669	8.7016
8.5	1.45 "	2.40 "	0.5782	8.6369
8.6	1.46 "	2.56 "	0.5113	8.6200
8.7	1.46 "	2.70 "	0.4052	8.5333

of log *k* were read directly from graphs at $\bar{n} = 1.5$ and were found to be 10.403 and 10.401 respectively for ZrO₂⁺-PAP and Th⁴⁺-PAP complexes.

The ratio of metal-ligand were also determined by pH-titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard NaOH. The ratio of metals to PAP was found to be 1 : 2. Therefore, in above calculations $\bar{n} = 1.5$ response to log *k*. In case of ZrO⁺⁺ the complexation occurs in the pH range 2.0-7.0, but in the case of Th⁴⁺ complexation occurs in the pH range 2.0-3.2 after that hydroxide formation takes place.

Acknowledgement

Author is thankful to Shri V. B. Sardesai, Principal, Bipin Bihari College, Jhansi, for encouragement, Dr. H. P. Agarwal and Dr. G. Viswnath of M.A.

TABLE 2—ZRO⁺⁺PAP COMPLEX

Total Volume	pH	ml. of NaOH	ml. of Ligand	Conc. of ligand moles/lit.				log (1/A)
				\bar{n}	Metal Bound	Free Ligand	Free Ligand ion conc.	
26.28 ml.	3.0	0.24 ml.	1.079 ml.	1.079	2.053 × 10 ⁻³	1.697 × 10 ⁻²	1.697 × 2.455 × 10 ⁻¹¹	10.3907
26.38 "	3.5	0.28 "	1.2589 "	1.2589	2.386 "	1.657 "	1.657 "	10.3910
26.47 "	4.0	0.32 "	1.4367 "	1.4367	2.714 "	1.618 "	1.618 "	10.4010
26.54 "	4.5	0.38 "	1.7065 "	1.7065	3.214 "	1.563 "	1.563 "	10.4161
26.58 "	5.0	0.38 "	1.7065 "	1.7065	3.209 "	1.561 "	1.561 "	10.4166
26.64 "	5.5	0.40 "	1.798 "	1.798	3.375 "	1.539 "	1.539 "	10.4227
26.68 "	6.0	0.40 "	1.798 "	1.798	3.370 "	1.540 "	1.540 "	10.4225
26.73 "	6.5	0.41 "	1.843 "	1.843	3.442 "	1.526 "	1.526 "	10.4261
26.80 "	7.0	0.43 "	1.933 "	1.933	3.608 "	1.505 "	1.505 "	10.4525

TABLE 3—TH⁴⁺-PAP COMPLEX

Total Volume	pH	ml. of NaOH	ml. of Ligand	Conc. of ligand moles/lit.				log (1/A)
				\bar{n}	Metal Bound	Free Ligand	Free Ligand ion conc.	
25.74 ml.	2.0	0.16 ml.	0.719 ml.	0.719	1.396 × 10 ⁻³	1.803 × 10 ⁻²	1.803 × 2.455 × 10 ⁻¹¹	10.3541
25.94 "	2.2	0.24 "	1.079 "	1.079	2.080 "	1.720 "	1.720 "	10.3745
26.08 "	2.4	0.26 "	1.169 "	1.169	2.242 "	1.693 "	1.693 "	10.3813
26.20 "	2.6	0.28 "	1.259 "	1.259	2.403 "	1.668 "	1.668 "	10.3878
26.30 "	2.8	0.30 "	1.349 "	1.349	2.564 "	1.644 "	1.644 "	10.3939
26.38 "	3.0	0.34 "	1.529 "	1.529	2.898 "	1.606 "	1.606W "	10.4043
26.48 "	3.2	0.40 "	1.798 "	1.798	3.396 "	1.551 "	1.661 "	10.4195

Calvin and Mechior⁵ extension of Bjerrum's⁶ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes. At any pH the horizontal distances between the curves of sets II and III and sets II and IV measures quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of PAP ion complexed with metals. Hence a series of \bar{n} values at various pH were obtained alongwith various log (1/A) i.e., log *k*. Table 2 and 3 show above values respectively for ZrO⁺⁺-PAP and Th⁴⁺-PAP complexes.

On plotting \bar{n} against log (1/A) the formation curves were obtained for each metal complex. The values

College of Technology, Bhopal for necessary facilities and suggestions.

References

1. A. H. BLATT, 'Organic Synthesis', Vol. II, 1963, p. 522.
2. A. J. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry'.
3. L. G. VAN UITERT and G. H. HAAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
4. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
5. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3270.
6. J. BJERRUM, 'Metalmine-formation in aqueous solutions'. P. Hasse and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.